

Forestry Policy, Clean cooking transition, and Integrated Socio-Environmental planning in Rwanda

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Abstract	<i>Journal of Policy and Development Studies (JPDS)</i>
<p><i>Access to clean cooking energy and sustainable forest management are critical to climate mitigation and development in sub-Saharan Africa. This study examines policy coherence between forestry and clean cooking energy policies in Rwanda and its implications for integrated socio-environmental climate mitigation planning. Using a qualitative approach, the study combines document analysis of national forestry, energy, and development policies with key informant interviews and contextual secondary data. The findings revealed that while forestry and clean cooking policies are strategically aligned around sustainability and climate objectives, operational integration remains limited. Institutional coordination is moderate and largely project-based, constraining the combined effectiveness of both sectors. Persistent household reliance on biomass highlights the need for stronger cross-sectoral policy design. Overall, the study provides empirical insights into policy integration in practice and identifies practical entry points for strengthening climate-responsive development planning in Rwanda.</i></p>	<p>Vol. 19 Issue 4 (2025) ISSN(p) 1597-9385 ISSN (e) 2814-1091 Home page: https://www.ajol.info/index.php/jpds</p> <p>ARTICLE INFO:</p> <p>Keywords: Policy integration, Climate mitigation, Planning, clean energy, Environment, socio-environmental systems</p> <p>Received: 30th July 2025 Revised: 27th September 2025 Accepted: 28th October, 2025</p> <p><u>DOI</u> https://dx.doi.org/10.4314/jpds.v19i4.11</p>

1. Introduction

Globally, over 2.6 billion people still rely on traditional biomass fuels, such as firewood and charcoal, for cooking. This dependency on biomass energy has widespread environmental and health implications, contributing to deforestation, indoor air pollution, and significant carbon emissions (International Energy Agency [IEA], 2020). In sub-Saharan Africa, these challenges are particularly pronounced, with many countries struggling with the dual issue of energy access and environmental degradation (United Nations Environment Programme [UNEP], 2019). The demand for sustainable energy solutions is increasing, driven by both the need for clean cooking technologies and the urgency to address climate change and forest conservation (World Bank, 2020).

In the context of Africa, countries like Rwanda face unique challenges in balancing forest conservation with the growing demand for cooking fuels. While many African nations have made strides toward improving energy access, particularly through renewable energy sources, biomass continues to dominate the household energy landscape (Owen *et al.*, 2013). In Rwanda, over 80% of households depend on firewood for cooking, which has contributed to significant forest depletion and environmental degradation (Rwanda Energy Group [REG], 2020). These challenges are exacerbated by unsustainable wood harvesting practices, which threaten both forest cover and the long-term availability of fuelwood resources (Rwanda Environment Management Authority [REMA], 2018).

To address these issues, Rwanda has adopted progressive policies aimed at sustainable energy and forest management. The Rwanda National Forestry Policy (2018) focuses on increasing forest cover, promoting sustainable forest management, and reducing biomass reliance (MINIRENA, 2018). At the same time, the country has made considerable efforts to transition towards clean cooking solutions, including the promotion of clean cookstoves and the uptake of modern cooking fuels like LPG and electricity (World Bank, 2020). Despite these policies, there remains a lack of research on how Rwanda's forestry policy interacts with its broader energy policies, particularly in terms of facilitating the clean cooking transition.

The relationship between forestry policy and energy policy in Rwanda is critical to achieving the country's sustainable development goals. While the national forestry policy prioritizes environmental sustainability, there is limited understanding of how it aligns with Rwanda's clean cooking energy goals. In particular, the coherence between these policies has not been sufficiently explored, raising questions about whether the country's forestry governance supports or hinders efforts to transition to cleaner cooking options (Kigali, 2021). Policy integration across these sectors is vital, as misaligned policies could undermine efforts to both protect forest resources and achieve universal access to clean cooking by 2030 (Reed *et al.*, 2017).

Given the intertwined challenges of sustainable energy access, forest conservation, and climate change mitigation, understanding the coherence between forestry and energy policies is increasingly critical. In Rwanda, forestry policy and clean cooking energy strategies operate at the intersection of environmental governance, household energy behavior, and climate mitigation planning. However, these policy domains are often designed and implemented through sectoral silos, limiting their potential to function as an integrated socio-environmental system. This research therefore examines the extent to which Rwanda's forestry policy coherently supports the clean cooking energy transition, and how this interaction contributes to broader climate mitigation and sustainable development objectives.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Despite Rwanda's significant progress in promoting clean cooking energy solutions, biomass energy, particularly firewood, remains the primary cooking fuel for over 80% of households, contributing to deforestation and environmental degradation (Rwanda Energy Group [REG], 2020). The continued reliance on firewood accelerates forest depletion, increases greenhouse gas emissions, and worsens public health issues due to indoor air pollution (Rwanda Environment Management Authority [REMA], 2018). To address these challenges, Rwanda has implemented policies aimed at sustainable forest management and clean energy access, including the Rwanda National Forestry Policy (2018), which promotes reforestation and sustainable management of forest resources, and initiatives to increase the uptake of clean cookstoves and modern cooking fuels like LPG and electricity (MINIRENA, 2018; World Bank, 2020).

Despite the shared objectives of forest conservation, clean energy access, and climate change mitigation, Rwanda's forestry and clean cooking energy policies have largely evolved through parallel policy processes. Forestry policy primarily targets forest protection and restoration, while clean cooking initiatives emphasize reducing biomass use without systematically integrating sustainable forest management considerations. This limited policy coherence risks undermining the effectiveness of both sectors, weakening their combined contribution to climate mitigation, forest sustainability, and long-term energy planning. Without an integrated socio-environmental policy framework, gains in clean cooking adoption may occur without commensurate reductions in forest pressure or emissions.

1.3 Research Objectives

Main Objective: To examine policy coherence between Rwanda's forestry and clean cooking energy policies and assess their combined role in shaping integrated socio-environmental climate mitigation systems.

Specific Objectives:

1. To assess the degree of policy coherence between Rwanda's forestry and clean cooking energy policies.
2. To identify key synergies and conflicts affecting the forestry–energy nexus within Rwanda's socio-environmental system.
3. To evaluate how existing policy integration contributes to climate mitigation and sustainable development outcomes.
4. To propose policy integration pathways that strengthen clean cooking transitions while sustaining forest-based climate benefits.

1.4 Research questions

1. To what extent are Rwanda's forestry and clean cooking energy policies coherent?
2. What synergies and conflicts shape the forestry–clean cooking policy nexus?
3. How does policy coherence influence climate mitigation and sustainability outcomes in Rwanda?

4. What integrated policy approaches can strengthen socio-environmental climate mitigation systems?

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1. Forestry Policy

Definition and Scope of Forestry Policy

Forestry policy encompasses the set of objectives, legal frameworks, and regulatory measures that guide the management, conservation, and utilization of forest resources (FAO, 2010). It typically addresses issues such as forest protection, biodiversity conservation, land tenure, and the promotion of sustainable forest-based livelihoods. A robust forestry policy provides strategic direction for balancing environmental conservation with socio-economic development, recognizing forests as critical for climate regulation, water security, and rural development (Angelsen & Kaimowitz, 1999). The role of forestry policies in sustainable development is significant. They contribute to multiple Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), including climate action, life on land, and poverty reduction (United Nations, 2015). By ensuring sustainable forest management, forestry policies help mitigate climate change, preserve biodiversity, and support the livelihoods of millions of people who depend on forests globally.

Global vs. National Forestry Policies

Globally, forestry policies have increasingly shifted towards sustainability, participatory governance, and integrated landscape management (Sloan & Sayer, 2015). International frameworks such as the United Nations Forum on Forests (UNFF) and the Global Forest Goals advocate for cross-sectoral approaches that link forestry to energy, agriculture, and climate sectors. In Rwanda, forestry policy reflects many of these global trends but is tailored to national priorities. The country's policies emphasize reforestation, forest cover expansion, and the promotion of agroforestry to address deforestation, energy demand, and land degradation (Republic of Rwanda, 2018). Unlike some global frameworks that emphasize indigenous rights and carbon trading markets, Rwanda's forestry policies are more centrally managed and closely aligned with national development strategies such as Vision 2050 (Mugabowindekwe *et al.*, 2020).

Rwanda's Forestry Policy landscape

Rwanda's key forestry instruments include the 2018 National Forestry Policy, the Forest Law (2013), and the Forest Sector Strategic Plan (2018–2024). The 2018 National Forestry Policy particularly underscores the sustainable management of forests to enhance economic growth, environmental resilience, and social development (Republic of Rwanda, 2018). The policy objectives are centered on increasing forest cover, promoting sustainable land management, encouraging agroforestry practices, and strengthening institutional coordination (MINIRENA, 2018). Agroforestry is notably promoted as a dual strategy for enhancing agricultural productivity and restoring degraded lands. Despite these ambitions, challenges persist in policy implementation. Limited financial resources, capacity gaps at local government levels, and conflicts between forestry, agriculture, and energy policies hamper integrated approaches (Ndayambaje *et al.*, 2011). Moreover, balancing the demand for wood energy with conservation

goals remains a critical tension, especially in rural areas where biomass is the primary cooking energy source.

2.2. Clean cooking energy

Definition of Clean cooking energy

Clean cooking energy refers to energy sources and technologies that enable cooking with minimal health and environmental impact. This includes modern cooking fuels such as liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), biogas, and electricity, alongside clean cookstoves that significantly reduce indoor air pollution (Puzzolo *et al.*, 2016). Unlike traditional biomass fuels (e.g., firewood and charcoal), clean cooking technologies are designed to provide efficient combustion, lower emissions, and contribute to both environmental sustainability and public health (Woolley *et al.*, 2022). The International Energy Agency (IEA, 2020) identifies clean cooking as a critical component of global energy access, highlighting the importance of transitioning away from the use of solid biomass in households to improve health outcomes and reduce carbon emissions. Modern cooking technologies, combined with clean fuels, can dramatically improve cooking efficiency, reduce the time spent collecting fuel, and lower the environmental degradation associated with traditional cooking methods (Roth *et al.*, 2018).

Energy access and Poverty

Clean cooking is integral to addressing energy poverty, which affects approximately 3 billion people globally who rely on traditional cooking methods (IEA, 2020). In many developing countries, the use of polluting fuels for cooking contributes to poor health outcomes such as respiratory diseases, including pneumonia, bronchitis, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (WHO, 2018). Women and children, who are often the primary gatherers of firewood, also face increased exposure to harmful smoke and health risks (Thakur *et al.*, 2020). By promoting clean cooking, countries can alleviate not only health burdens but also economic poverty. Access to modern cooking solutions frees up time for other economic activities, particularly for women, while fostering cleaner and more productive environments. Furthermore, clean cooking technologies can stimulate local economies by creating job opportunities in manufacturing, distribution, and service sectors related to clean cookstoves and fuels (Rosenthal *et al.*, 2018).

Clean cooking energy in Rwanda

In Rwanda, clean cooking energy access has become a priority for achieving sustainable development. According to the Rwanda Energy Group (REG, 2020), over 80% of households rely on traditional biomass for cooking, contributing to deforestation, indoor air pollution, and high health costs. The government has recognized the need for a transition to cleaner fuels and technologies to meet its climate goals and enhance public health. Several government policies and initiatives have been launched to promote clean cooking in Rwanda. The National Clean Cooking Strategy (2019) outlines a roadmap to increase access to cleaner cooking technologies, such as improved cookstoves, biogas, and LPG (MININFRA, 2019). The strategy targets a significant reduction in the use of traditional biomass by promoting the adoption of cleaner, more efficient cooking options. One notable initiative is the distribution of subsidized improved cookstoves,

which help reduce fuel consumption and emissions (Rwanda Environment Management Authority, 2021). The government has also focused on scaling up biogas production and expanding the use of LPG, particularly in urban areas, as part of its broader energy access framework (MININFRA, 2020). However, challenges remain in reaching rural households where affordability, infrastructure, and awareness pose barriers to the adoption of these technologies (Ruzibiza *et al.*, 2022).

2.3. The Interplay between Forestry Policies and Clean cooking energy

Synergies between Forestry and Energy Policies

Well-managed forest resources can play a pivotal role in supporting the transition to clean cooking energy. Sustainable forestry practices, such as agroforestry and reforestation, contribute to the production of cleaner biomass sources that can be used in cooking without causing environmental degradation (Guta, 2014). For example, producing efficient firewood or charcoal from sustainably managed forests can help reduce the pressure on natural forests while providing an affordable and cleaner energy source for cooking. The integration of forestry and energy policies can lead to better management of woodfuel resources, enhancing the environmental and economic benefits of clean cooking initiatives (Woolley *et al.*, 2022). There are also significant opportunities for promoting renewable energy through sustainable biomass use. Biomass-based technologies such as improved cookstoves, bioethanol, and biogas offer low-carbon alternatives to traditional cooking methods (Thakur *et al.*, 2020). When combined with sustainable forest management practices, biomass can be produced in a way that supports both energy needs and environmental goals. For instance, waste-to-energy projects and small-scale biogas installations can reduce reliance on unsustainable biomass while simultaneously providing clean energy (Puzzolo *et al.*, 2016). Additionally, the growing interest in integrated rural energy solutions offers the potential to link energy production with forest conservation efforts, fostering circular economies that benefit both the energy and forestry sectors.

Conflicts and Trade-offs

Despite the synergies, there are significant conflicts and trade-offs between forest preservation and the demand for fuelwood for cooking. In many developing countries, including Rwanda, the overwhelming reliance on traditional biomass fuels for cooking leads to unsustainable rates of deforestation (UNEP, 2020). This fuelwood demand exacerbates forest degradation and reduces carbon sequestration, which in turn threatens biodiversity and contributes to climate change (Newbold *et al.*, 2015). The challenge lies in balancing the need for fuelwood, particularly in rural areas, with the long-term goal of forest conservation and ecosystem restoration. Efforts to reduce deforestation, such as promoting alternative cooking fuels, can be undermined by the continued reliance on wood-based biomass without effective regulation and sustainable production practices (Zulu & Richardson, 2013). Balancing development goals is another critical issue. On one hand, access to clean cooking energy is essential for improving health and economic development, particularly for women and children who are disproportionately affected by the harmful effects of traditional cooking methods (Roth *et al.*, 2018). On the other hand, environmental conservation policies often restrict the use of forest resources, which can create tensions between immediate energy needs and long-term environmental sustainability. In Rwanda, for example, while there are

ambitious goals for forest conservation and reforestation, the country also faces substantial pressure to expand energy access, particularly in rural communities that heavily depend on fuelwood for cooking (Republic of Rwanda, 2018). Finding a balance that simultaneously promotes energy access and environmental protection is a key challenge that requires coherent policy frameworks and integrated approaches across sectors (Puzzolo *et al.*, 2016).

2.4. Theoretical review

Policy integration theories

Policy integration refers to the process of aligning and coordinating policies across multiple sectors or governance levels to achieve coherent, effective outcomes. This is particularly critical in cases like Rwanda, where cross-sectoral issues, such as forestry and clean cooking energy, are inherently interconnected (Lafferty & Hovden, 2003). Policy integration facilitates the development of holistic solutions that address complex challenges, such as environmental sustainability and energy access, which cannot be effectively addressed by siloed policies (Nilsson *et al.*, 2012). In the context of Rwanda's forestry and energy sectors, integration helps bridge the gap between forest conservation efforts and clean cooking initiatives, ensuring that policies complement rather than contradict each other.

Types of integration

1. Horizontal Integration: Coordination across sectors

Horizontal integration involves aligning policies across related sectors to foster synergy and minimize conflicts. In the context of Rwanda, this would mean aligning forestry policies with energy policies to ensure that the promotion of clean cooking fuels does not undermine forest conservation goals (O'Toole, 2000). Effective horizontal integration requires comprehensive planning and cooperation among different ministries and agencies, ensuring that the goals of each sector, such as forest conservation and energy access, are not working at cross-purposes. The integration of forest management policies with energy access policies can also promote the use of sustainable biomass as a cleaner cooking fuel while preserving forest ecosystems.

2. Vertical Integration: Alignment between governance levels

Vertical integration focuses on aligning policies across different levels of governance, from national policies down to local implementation. In Rwanda, this type of integration ensures that national policies, such as the 2018 National Forestry Policy, are translated effectively into local actions. Local governments and community organizations must play an active role in implementing national objectives, such as increasing clean cooking energy access and sustainable forest management (Trein *et al.*, 2023). Vertical integration is essential for overcoming local barriers to the adoption of clean cooking technologies and forest management practices, ensuring that policy initiatives reach the communities most in need.

3. Sectoral Integration: Cohesion within a single sector

Sectoral integration involves ensuring that policies within a single sector (such as energy or forestry) are cohesive and mutually reinforcing. For example, Rwanda's energy policy could benefit from stronger integration with forestry policies by encouraging the use of sustainable biomass and improved cookstoves, which reduce deforestation while providing cleaner cooking alternatives. Similarly, within the forestry sector, policies related to agroforestry, land management, and forest restoration should be integrated to promote sustainable land use practices that contribute to both environmental and energy goals (Falcone, 2023).

Models of Policy coherence

1. The Policy Coherence for Development (PCD) Framework

The Policy Coherence for Development (PCD) framework emphasizes the need for aligning policies across sectors to promote sustainable development, particularly in developing countries (European Commission, 2013). In Rwanda's case, PCD could guide the integration of forest management and clean cooking policies by ensuring that environmental policies, such as deforestation control measures, do not hinder the progress of clean cooking initiatives. It stresses the importance of aligning development objectives across sectors to prevent contradictions and promote long-term sustainability.

2. Integrated Policy design

Integrated Policy Design advocates for a comprehensive, unified strategy that incorporates multiple sectors into a single framework (Jordan & Huitema, 2014). This approach is highly relevant to the issue of clean cooking and forestry, as it allows for the development of policies that address both energy access and environmental conservation simultaneously. For example, Rwanda could implement an integrated policy that supports the use of sustainable biomass for cooking while promoting forest restoration and rural development through agroforestry practices. This design would require a systemic approach to policy-making, where energy, agriculture, and forestry sectors work collaboratively toward shared objectives.

3. Sustainable Development Theory

Sustainable development (SD) refers to the approach of fostering economic growth, social inclusion, and environmental protection in a way that meets present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own (Brundtland, 1987). The three core pillars of sustainable development (economic, social, and environmental) are interconnected and must be pursued simultaneously to achieve a balanced, long-term development model. Economic sustainability focuses on fostering economic growth and prosperity, while social sustainability emphasizes social equity, inclusion, and improved quality of life. Environmental sustainability, meanwhile, ensures that natural resources are used efficiently and conserved for future generations (United Nations, 2015).

In the context of Rwanda, sustainable development is central to national policy, particularly in sectors like forestry and energy. Both sustainable forest management and the transition to clean cooking energy play critical roles in ensuring that the country's development remains aligned with

these three pillars. For instance, the sustainable management of forest resources helps preserve biodiversity, maintain carbon sequestration capacities, and support the livelihoods of rural populations, contributing to both environmental and social sustainability goals (Kuyper *et al.*, 2016).

Sustainability in Policy making

Integrated policy-making is essential for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) and SDG 13 (Climate Action). These goals focus on ensuring universal access to clean, affordable energy while mitigating the impacts of climate change. Policies must balance the trade-offs between development goals, such as improving energy access through clean cooking and preserving forests for carbon sequestration and biodiversity (Barton *et al.*, 2019).

In Rwanda, integrated policies that link energy and forest management objectives are crucial for advancing these SDGs. For example, the promotion of clean cooking technologies like biogas and LPG not only provides clean energy access (SDG 7) but also reduces pressure on forests, mitigating deforestation and greenhouse gas emissions (SDG 13). However, the challenge lies in ensuring that the benefits of such integrated policies are equitably distributed, especially to marginalized populations that depend on traditional biomass fuels for cooking (Newbold *et al.*, 2015). This underscores the importance of balancing development goals with environmental protection and social inclusion, ensuring that no group is left behind in the transition to a sustainable energy future.

Linking forestry and clean cooking to Sustainability

Sustainable forest management (SFM) is fundamental to achieving environmental sustainability and poverty alleviation. SFM involves practices that ensure forest resources are used in a way that maintains forest health, preserves biodiversity, and supports ecosystem services (FAO, 2017). In Rwanda, sustainable forestry practices, such as agroforestry and reforestation, contribute to environmental sustainability by reducing deforestation, promoting carbon sequestration, and enhancing the resilience of local communities to climate change (Republic of Rwanda, 2018). Furthermore, sustainable forest management helps secure livelihoods for rural populations that depend on forests for fuelwood, food, and other resources.

The role of clean cooking energy in advancing sustainability is equally significant. Clean cooking technologies, such as improved cookstoves and biogas, improve health by reducing indoor air pollution and decrease the time spent collecting firewood, especially for women and children. These technologies also support environmental sustainability by reducing the demand for unsustainable fuelwood and forest degradation (Puzzolo *et al.*, 2016). By addressing health and environmental issues simultaneously, clean cooking energy contributes to both the social and environmental dimensions of sustainability, aligning with the goals of SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) and SDG 13 (Climate Action).

Environmental governance in Rwanda

Environmental governance refers to the frameworks and structures for managing shared resources, policies, and programs aimed at achieving sustainability (Ostrom, 2009). In Rwanda, governance structures are designed to support sustainable forest management and energy access by promoting integrated approaches that involve multiple stakeholders at local, national, and regional levels. The role of governance in sustainable development is particularly evident in the management of forests and the promotion of clean cooking technologies, where coordination across sectors and governance levels is essential for achieving policy coherence and effective implementation.

At the national level, Rwanda has implemented strong environmental governance frameworks, such as the National Forest Policy (2018) and the National Clean Cooking Strategy (2019), which align energy and forestry policies with sustainability goals. However, challenges remain in the integration of these policies at local levels, where enforcement and coordination may be weaker (Barton *et al.*, 2019). This highlights the need for multi-level governance systems that ensure the policies enacted at the national level are effectively implemented at local levels, ensuring that sustainable development goals are met across different regions and communities.

Institutional Theory and Policy implementation

Institutional Theory

Institutional theory explores how both formal and informal institutions shape policy processes, including their design, implementation, and outcomes. Formal institutions consist of established rules, laws, and regulations, while informal institutions include social norms, values, and practices that influence behavior within a society (North, 1990). In the context of policy implementation, institutional theory emphasizes the interaction between these formal and informal structures, highlighting how they collectively influence the effectiveness of policy execution and coordination (Hall & Taylor, 1996).

In terms of forestry and energy policies in Rwanda, institutional theory helps us understand how the country's legal frameworks, such as the 2018 National Forestry Policy and the National Clean Cooking Strategy, interact with societal practices and values around forest resource use and cooking technologies. For example, while the law may mandate the use of cleaner fuels and sustainable forest management practices, informal social norms may still prioritize traditional cooking methods and fuelwood collection, posing challenges to policy implementation and sustainability (Ostrom, 2009). Thus, both formal and informal institutions must be aligned to ensure the effective implementation of policy goals.

Institutional frameworks for Policy integration

Institutional frameworks are critical in fostering or hindering the coherence between forestry and energy policies. These frameworks include the structures, rules, and procedures that guide decision-making and interactions between various policy actors (Sabatier, 2007). In Rwanda, the institutional framework for forestry and energy policy integration involves multiple stakeholders, including government agencies, local authorities, NGOs, and community organizations, each with distinct roles in policy implementation.

Effective policy integration requires these institutions to coordinate their actions, share information, and collaborate to ensure that the policies are mutually reinforcing rather than conflicting (Cejudo & Michel, 2017). For example, the alignment of energy access policies with forest management strategies depends on strong institutional cooperation between Rwanda's Ministry of Environment, the Rwanda Energy Group, and local communities. These collaborations can drive the successful implementation of integrated policies, such as promoting sustainable biomass for clean cooking while maintaining forest conservation goals. Conversely, weak institutional coordination or conflicting institutional objectives can lead to fragmentation, reducing the efficacy of policy integration and hindering progress toward sustainability goals (Pahl-Wostl, 2009).

Moreover, multi-stakeholder collaboration is essential to driving successful policy integration. Institutions that foster collaboration; whether formal agreements or informal networks, enable diverse actors to contribute their knowledge and resources toward achieving shared goals. However, challenges arise when there are conflicting priorities or when the interests of powerful stakeholders outweigh those of marginalized groups, such as rural communities dependent on traditional cooking methods. Thus, institutional frameworks must ensure inclusive participation and balance the power dynamics between stakeholders to achieve coherent and effective policy integration (Gunningham *et al.*, 2009).

Institutional barriers and enablers in Policy implementation

In the context of policy implementation, institutional theory also helps identify barriers and enablers to effective policy execution. Institutional barriers may arise when there is a lack of capacity within institutions to implement policies or when there are inconsistencies in the policy landscape (Birkland, 2015). For instance, limited institutional capacity at the local level could hinder the implementation of clean cooking policies, even if national policies are well-defined. Similarly, fragmented governance structures between the forestry and energy sectors can create conflicts or gaps in policy enforcement. On the other hand, institutional enablers, such as clear regulatory frameworks, strong enforcement mechanisms, and a commitment to cross-sectoral collaboration, can significantly enhance policy implementation (Mayntz, 2009). In Rwanda, efforts to integrate forestry and clean cooking policies could benefit from strengthening institutions at both national and local levels to promote a more cohesive, collaborative approach that ensures effective policy delivery and sustainability.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Design

A descriptive and exploratory approach was employed, incorporating both qualitative and supplementary quantitative elements. A descriptive design was suitable because it aimed to provide an accurate portrayal of the relationship between Rwanda's forestry policy and clean cooking energy policies, helping to identify key themes, trends, and issues in policy integration and policy outcomes (Bryman, 2016). The exploratory aspect of the design was employed to investigate areas where limited research had been conducted, particularly on how policies from two important distinct sectors interacted to influence sustainable development in Rwanda. This

approach allowed the study to uncover underlying mechanisms, policy synergies, and potential conflicts not thoroughly examined in previous literature (Creswell, 2014). Through this design, the research examined the effectiveness of policy integration in achieving sustainable development goals, with particular focus on the overlap and interaction between forestry and energy policies.

The study's design was predominantly qualitative, focusing on understanding complex social phenomena such as policy formulation, implementation, and the institutional dynamics shaping interactions between the forestry and energy sectors. A qualitative approach was particularly fitting for capturing the perspectives of key stakeholders and gaining a richer understanding of policy coherence (Patton, 2002). Document analysis and key informant interviews formed the core of data collection, while secondary quantitative data were selectively incorporated to provide contextual support, illustrate trends, and inform policy-relevant implications without serving as a basis for statistical modeling. This integrated design ensured that both the depth of qualitative insight and the contextual perspective offered by quantitative indicators were considered in the analysis.

3.2. Data types

The study used a predominantly qualitative research design, supported by selectively employed quantitative data, to examine the coherence between Rwanda's forestry and clean cooking energy policies. Emphasis was placed on qualitative inquiry as the primary means of understanding policy alignment, institutional interactions, and governance dynamics, while quantitative data were used in a supplementary capacity to contextualize findings and inform broader policy implications rather than to serve as a basis for statistical modeling or numerical analysis. This methodology is rigorous for policy examination studies (Creswell, 2014).

Qualitative data

The core of the analysis was grounded in qualitative data derived from policy documents, government reports, and interviews with key stakeholders across the forestry and energy sectors. These sources provided in-depth insights into policy intent, implementation processes, and intersectoral coordination, enabling an assessment of policy coherence and the identification of institutional, regulatory, and governance factors influencing outcomes (Patton, 2015). This qualitative approach facilitated the exploration of synergies and tensions between forestry conservation objectives and clean cooking energy strategies, with particular attention to how these policies are interpreted and operationalized in practice.

Quantitative data

Secondary quantitative data including indicators related to deforestation rates and clean cooking energy uptake were incorporated in a limited and supportive role. Rather than serving as a standalone analytical foundation, these data were used to corroborate qualitative findings and to inform the development of policy-relevant implications. In this way, quantitative evidence functioned as contextual support, enhancing the interpretive depth of the qualitative analysis without constituting a numerical basis for further statistical examination (Babbie, 2021).

3.3 Data collection methods

One key method was document analysis, where a range of policy documents, government publications, and reports related to both Rwanda's forestry management and clean cooking energy policies were reviewed. This analysis focused on primary documents such as the National Forestry Policy (2018), the National Strategy for Transformation (NST1), and other energy strategies. By analyzing these documents, the study was able to identify policy objectives, the alignment (or lack thereof) between the two sectors, and potential areas for improving policy coherence (Costa-Campi *et al.*, 2017).

In addition, key informant interviews were conducted with relevant stakeholders in both the forestry and energy sectors. These individuals have been chosen for their expertise and involvement in the development and implementation of policies related to sustainable energy and forest management. These interviews provided an in-depth qualitative perspective on the challenges, synergies, and conflicts in policy integration (King, Keohane, & Verba, 1994). The open format of the interviews allowed for flexibility in exploring specific areas of interest while still ensuring that essential topics are covered.

To supplement the primary data, secondary data analysis was utilized. This involved gathering quantitative data from various reputable sources, such as the Rwanda Environment Management Authority (REMA), the Rwanda Energy Group (REG), local NGOs, local authorities and international organizations like the World Bank. This data provided valuable insights into key operational aspects of this research. Secondary data offers a cost-effective way to analyze trends and patterns that reflect the success of Rwanda's policy efforts over time (Bryman, 2016).

3.4 Population and sampling frame

The population for this study consisted of key individuals and institutions involved in the development, implementation, and evaluation of Rwanda's forestry and clean cooking energy policies. This included government officials, policymakers, experts from NGOs, and other stakeholders engaged in sustainable energy and forest management. The sampling frame was constructed from institutional directories, public records, and other sources listing individuals and organizations involved in these policy areas. The focus was on participants with deep knowledge of the policies and direct involvement in their design and implementation. This approach ensured that the study captured informed perspectives on the complexities of policy integration and its impacts (Flick, 2014).

Given the qualitative focus and the need for in-depth interviews with key informants, the study targeted 24–32 participants, a range supported in qualitative research as sufficient for capturing diverse insights while remaining manageable (Guest *et al.*, 2006). This size allowed for data saturation, where no new themes emerged, ensuring a robust understanding of policy interactions.

3.5 Sampling strategy and sample size calculation

A purposive sampling strategy was employed, selecting participants with relevant expertise and experience in forestry and clean cooking energy policies. Purposive sampling is well-suited for qualitative research, where the goal is in-depth understanding rather than statistical generalization (Patton, 2002). Key informants included officials from the Ministry of Environment, Ministry of Energy, and Ministry of Agriculture, as well as experts from NGOs and international organizations working in energy access, clean cooking, and forest conservation. The chosen sample size of 24–32 participants allowed for a balance between diversity of perspectives and practical constraints such as time and budget. For document analysis and secondary data, no formal sample size was calculated, as all relevant documents and datasets were reviewed comprehensively to provide a clear picture of the policy landscape and its outcomes.

3.6 Data analysis methods

The collected data were analyzed using both qualitative and quantitative techniques to provide a comprehensive understanding of policy integration and outcomes. Thematic analysis was employed to identify key themes, patterns, and issues emerging from key informant interviews and document analysis. This approach revealed how Rwanda's forestry and energy policies were aligned and highlighted any synergies or conflicts between them. Themes were organized according to the research questions, allowing a systematic exploration of policy integration and barriers to sustainable development (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Content analysis of policy documents identified specific goals, strategies, and measures related to forestry and clean cooking energy. By quantifying the presence of key terms and concepts, this method assessed the extent to which policies addressed sustainability, energy access, and forest conservation (Neuendorf, 2017).

3.9 Ethical considerations

Ethical considerations were central to the integrity of the research. First, informed consent was obtained from all participants involved in interviews. Participants received a detailed explanation of the study's objectives, methods, and potential risks, and they retained the right to withdraw at any time without consequence. Second, confidentiality was strictly maintained. All interview data were anonymized, ensuring that no personal identifiers appeared in the final report, and data were securely stored with access limited only to the researcher. Third, the study ensured that participants experienced no harm. Interviews were conducted respectfully, and participants could skip questions they found uncomfortable. Care was taken to avoid exacerbating any existing conflicts or tensions within the sectors studied. Finally, the research adhered to principles of academic integrity. All sources were properly cited, and any conflicts of interest were disclosed. Ethical approval was obtained from the relevant institutional review board to ensure compliance with required ethical standards.

4. Result

4.1 Profile of key informants

Key informant interviews were conducted with a purposively selected group of stakeholders ($n = 26$) drawn from forestry governance, energy planning, clean cooking initiatives, environmental

conservation organizations, and academia in Rwanda. Participants included policymakers from the Rwanda Forestry Authority, technical experts managing conservation and landscape-level interventions, practitioners involved in clean cooking program implementation, an energy planning professional from the Rwanda Energy Group, and academic experts in forestry and environmental studies. Respondents possessed between approximately 5 and over 20 years average of professional experience in policy formulation, implementation, research, or program management. Their diverse institutional positions enabled the study to capture perspectives across strategic, operational, and analytical levels of the forestry–energy policy landscape.

4.2 Evidence from Policy and strategy documents

4.2.1 Policy objectives and areas of convergence

Analysis of national policy documents, including the National Forestry Policy (2018), the National Strategy for Transformation (NST1), and relevant clean cooking and energy strategies, reveals a shared commitment to sustainable development and climate change mitigation. Forestry policy emphasizes forest conservation, restoration, and sustainable management, while clean cooking and energy strategies prioritize reducing reliance on traditional biomass, improving household energy efficiency, and lowering emissions (Republic of Rwanda, 2018; Republic of Rwanda, 2017).

Across documents, clean cooking transitions are implicitly positioned as supportive of forest conservation objectives, particularly through reduced fuelwood and charcoal demand. Similarly, forestry policy frameworks acknowledge the importance of sustainable energy alternatives in alleviating pressure on forest resources. At this strategic level, policy alignment is evident in overarching goals and national development narratives.

4.2.2 Gaps in Operational Integration

Despite this convergence at the objective level, analysis indicates *limited operational integration* between forestry and clean cooking policies. Forestry policy instruments focus primarily on land use planning, forest protection, and restoration targets, with relatively limited reference to household energy transitions as an integral component of forest sustainability. Conversely, clean cooking strategies prioritize energy access, health, and technology dissemination, with less explicit linkage to forest management planning or monitoring indicators (Republic of Rwanda, 2018; Republic of Rwanda, 2017).

The analysis further shows that sector-specific policy documents are developed and updated on *different timelines*, contributing to inconsistencies in how cross-sectoral priorities are articulated. These gaps suggest that policy coherence remains stronger in principle than in implementation design.

4.3 Forestry–Energy linkages in practice: insights from key informant interviews

4.3.1 Household cooking energy and forest pressure

Interview findings reinforce the document analysis by *highlighting household cooking energy demand as a major driver of forest resource pressure* in Rwanda. Respondents consistently described biomass [particularly fuelwood and charcoal] as central to household energy use, especially in rural and peri-urban areas. Informants emphasized that even where national forest cover has increased, localized forest degradation linked to biomass extraction persists.

Several respondents noted that clean cooking initiatives have begun to alter this dynamic, but progress remains uneven. In their view, forest conservation outcomes are closely tied to the pace, affordability, and social acceptance of clean cooking technologies.

4.3.2 Perceived Policy coherence and fragmentation

Consistent with documentary findings, key informants characterized policy coherence between forestry and clean cooking energy as *partial and uneven*. While respondents acknowledged shared national goals, they emphasized that coordination often occurs through *project-based or donor-driven mechanisms* rather than through institutionalized policy integration. Examples of synergy were identified in localized interventions where clean cooking deployment coincides with forest restoration or conservation projects. However, respondents also cited instances where clean cooking programs operate independently of forestry planning, limiting their long-term environmental impact. Inferred synergies lingered to be conceptual and not existent.

4.4 Governance and institutional coordination

4.4.1 Institutional coordination effectiveness

Both documentary evidence and interview responses suggest that coordination between institutions responsible for forestry and clean cooking energy is *moderate but not fully effective*. Formal coordination platforms exist at the national level, yet respondents observed that these mechanisms do not consistently translate into joint planning, harmonized indicators, or shared monitoring frameworks. As a result, policy integration is often dependent on individual initiatives or external funding arrangements rather than embedded governance structures.

4.4.2 Identified institutional challenges

Key informants and document analysis jointly point to several constraints affecting policy coherence. These included *infrequent policy updates, limited integration of cross-sectoral evidence during policy formulation, and insufficient baseline data* linking biomass consumption, forest condition, and clean cooking adoption. Additional challenges highlighted by respondents include capacity constraints for cross-sectoral planning and unclear institutional mandates at implementation levels. Local governments and communities were consistently identified as critical actors in implementation. However, respondents noted that decentralized authorities often lack sufficient guidance and resources to operationalize integrated forestry–energy strategies effectively.

4.5 Trends from secondary data sources

Review of secondary data from national institutions and international sources indicated gradual progress in clean cooking adoption alongside sustained forest conservation efforts. Data trends suggested reductions in reliance on traditional biomass in some contexts, alongside ongoing forest restoration and management initiatives (REMA, 2022; REG, 2021). However, these trends also reveal *persistent biomass dependence* among significant portions of the population, underscoring the importance of policy coherence in translating clean cooking adoption into measurable forest and emissions outcomes (World Bank, 2022; REMA, 2022). While this study does not undertake statistical analysis, the secondary data provide contextual evidence that complements documentary and interview findings.

4.6 Climate Mitigation implications across evidence sources

Across all the data sources, findings converged on the conclusion that forestry and clean cooking policies contribute meaningfully to Rwanda’s climate mitigation agenda, as articulated in national climate, forestry, and energy planning frameworks (Republic of Rwanda, 2018; REMA, 2022). Nevertheless, limited operational integration constrains the potential for these sectors to function as a fully integrated socio-environmental climate mitigation system.

5. Discussion

5.1 Policy coherence as a foundation for Integrated Climate Mitigation Systems

The findings indicate that Rwanda’s forestry and clean cooking energy policies are at a good extent *strategically aligned but operationally fragmented*. At the level of national vision and development planning, both policy domains articulate shared commitments to sustainability, emissions reduction, and socio-economic transformation (Republic of Rwanda, 2017, 2018). This alignment reflects what policy integration theory describes as *horizontal coherence*; consistency of objectives across sectors (Candel & Biesbroek, 2016). As shown in Figure 1, Rwanda’s policies demonstrate strong strategic alignment but limited operational integration.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework illustrating the gap between strategic alignment and operational integration in Rwanda’s forestry and clean cooking energy policies.

POLICY COHERENCE FRAMEWORK
Strategic Alignment with National objectives <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Forestry: forest protection, restoration- Clean Cooking: adoption, health, technology dissemination
Operational Fragmentation in Implementation <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Weak linkages between sectors- Independent programs at local level
Integrated Climate Mitigation System goal <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Functional policy synergy- Emissions reduction + forest conservation

Source: Author’s original design

However, the results demonstrate that this coherence weakens at the level of implementation design. Forestry policies emphasize land use planning, forest restoration, and protection mechanisms, while clean cooking strategies prioritize energy access, health, and technology

dissemination. The absence of explicit operational linkages limits the ability of these policies to function collectively as a unified climate mitigation system. This gap highlights the distinction between symbolic integration and functional integration, where shared goals exist without corresponding coordination mechanisms (Nilsson et al., 2012).

5.2 Forestry–Energy linkages and the Socio-Environmental System perspective

Interview findings underscore that household cooking energy demand remains a critical driver of forest resource pressure in Rwanda, particularly through continued reliance on biomass fuels. From a socio-environmental systems perspective, this relationship reflects a feedback loop in which energy practices directly shape ecological outcomes, while forest conditions influence energy availability and livelihoods. Figure 2 illustrates how household energy demand directly influences forest pressure, creating a feedback loop with implications for policy integration.

Figure 2. Feedback loop between household cooking energy demand and forest resource pressure in Rwanda.

Source: Author’s original design

While national forest cover statistics suggest improvement, respondents emphasized localized degradation linked to fuelwood and charcoal extraction, echoing concerns raised in national environmental assessments (REMA, 2022). This divergence between aggregate indicators and localized realities reinforces the importance of systems-based analysis in climate mitigation planning. Without integrating clean cooking transitions into forest management strategies, emissions reductions and conservation gains risk remaining partial or spatially uneven. These findings align with broader literature arguing that climate mitigation effectiveness depends not only on sectoral interventions but also on how social behavior, resource use, and environmental governance interact over time (Ostrom, 2009).

5.3 Institutional coordination and the limits of sectoral governance

The study's results indicate that institutional coordination between forestry and clean cooking energy actors in Rwanda remains *moderate but weakly institutionalized*. While inter-agency platforms, joint task forces, and collaborative projects do exist, coordination is predominantly *project-based and donor-driven*, rather than embedded within routine planning, budgeting, and monitoring processes. As summarized in Table 1, most actors operate within parallel governance tracks, with limited mechanisms to ensure sustained cross-sectoral alignment.

From an institutional theory perspective, this pattern reflects the persistence of *sectoral silos*, whereby organizations continue to function according to established mandates, incentive structures, and reporting hierarchies (North, 1990). Forestry institutions prioritize conservation and restoration outcomes, while energy institutions focus on access, infrastructure, and technology deployment. In the absence of binding coordination rules, shared performance indicators, or integrated data systems, cross-sectoral collaboration remains largely discretionary. Consequently, policy coherence depends less on formal governance arrangements and more on individual leadership, short-term projects, or externally financed initiatives.

The findings further revealed that coordination gaps are reinforced by *fragmented knowledge and information streams*. Universities, research institutions, and technical experts primarily play advisory roles, with limited institutionalized pathways for translating evidence into policy design or implementation. Similarly, non-state actors (particularly NGOs and private sector clean cooking providers) engage selectively across sectors, often without clear incentives to integrate sustainable biomass supply or forest restoration objectives into clean cooking programs. This results in missed opportunities to align demand-side energy interventions with supply-side forest sustainability.

Local governments and communities occupy a *pivotal yet constrained position* within this governance landscape. As decentralized implementers, districts and lower administrative units are tasked with operationalizing both forest management and clean cooking initiatives, yet they frequently lack the financial resources, technical capacity, and clear guidance necessary to pursue integrated approaches. Weak vertical coordination between national policy frameworks and local implementation structures further limits the translation of policy coherence into practice. Without clearer mandates, harmonized planning tools, and sustained capacity-building at the local level, integration risks remaining aspirational rather than operational.

Therefore, this study suggests that improving coordination between forestry and clean cooking energy sectors in Rwanda requires moving beyond ad hoc collaboration toward *durable institutional arrangements*. This includes formalized inter-ministerial coordination mechanisms, shared monitoring frameworks, and incentive structures that reward cross-sectoral outcomes. Strengthening such institutional foundations is essential for addressing the underlying governance constraints identified in this study and for ensuring that clean cooking transitions contribute meaningfully to long-term forest sustainability.

Table 1. Overview of key consulted representative institutions, mandates, and identified coordination gaps between forestry and clean cooking energy sectors in Rwanda.

Institution / Actor	Mandate / Role	Coordination status	Key gap / Observation
Rwanda Forestry Authority (RFA)	Forest governance, sustainable forest management, reforestation and restoration	Moderate	Forestry considerations insufficiently mainstreamed into clean cooking and household energy planning
Rwanda Energy Group (REG)	Energy access expansion, clean cooking promotion, infrastructure development	Moderate	Clean cooking initiatives insufficiently aligned with sustainable biomass supply and forest conservation objectives
Ministry of Environment (MoE)	Environmental policy oversight, climate change mitigation, natural resource governance	Moderate	Limited operational linkage with energy-sector implementation agencies
Ministry of Infrastructure (MININFRA)	National energy policy formulation and coordination	Moderate	Sectoral silos limit integrated planning between energy access and forest sustainability
Albertine Rift Conservation Society (NGO)	Biodiversity conservation, forest protection, community-based natural resource management	Limited	Conservation programs weakly connected to clean cooking and household energy interventions
Del Agua (NGO)	Clean cooking implementation, health and environmental co-benefits	Ad hoc	Limited integration of forest sustainability indicators into clean cooking program design
Other Clean Cooking NGOs / CSOs	Stove dissemination, awareness raising, behavior change	Variable	Fragmentation across projects; limited coordination with national forestry strategies
Private Sector (Cookstove & Fuel Suppliers)	Production and distribution of improved cookstoves and alternative fuels	Limited–Moderate	Weak incentives to source sustainably produced biomass or engage in forest restoration

Development Partners / Donors	Financing, technical assistance, pilot projects	Project-based	Short project cycles constrain long-term institutional coordination
Local Governments (Districts, Sectors, Cells, Villages)	Local-level implementation, enforcement, community mobilization	Variable	Capacity constraints and unclear mandates across forestry and energy responsibilities
Universities / Research Institutions	Technical analysis, policy research, monitoring and evaluation	Advisory	Research inputs not systematically embedded in policy and program design
Community Cooperatives / User Groups	Biomass production, forest use, local energy adoption	Informal	Limited formal recognition in national coordination mechanisms

Source: Author’s original compilation from Primary and Secondary Data

5.4. Climate Mitigation implications of partial policy integration

Across all data sources, the findings converge on the inference that forestry and clean cooking policies in Rwanda make *meaningful but under-optimized contributions* to the national climate mitigation agenda. Forestry policies support carbon sequestration and ecosystem resilience, while clean cooking initiatives offer pathways to reduce emissions from biomass combustion and to slow forest degradation (Republic of Rwanda, 2018; REMA, 2022).

However, *limited operational integration constrains the cumulative mitigation potential* of these efforts by weakening feedbacks between household energy demand reduction and sustainable biomass supply systems. Secondary data indicate gradual improvements in clean cooking adoption; nevertheless, persistent reliance on traditional biomass suggests that emissions reductions and forest pressure alleviation are not occurring at the scale required to meet long-term mitigation targets (World Bank, 2022). Stronger policy coherence could amplify mitigation outcomes by explicitly aligning clean cooking targets with forest conservation indicators and embedding household energy transitions within long-term land-use and climate planning frameworks.

As summarized in Table 2, while policy objectives across the forestry and clean cooking domains are broadly aligned, *operational linkages remain weak*, limiting the cumulative impact on climate mitigation. This finding supports arguments in the climate policy literature that *integration across mitigation pathways* is critical for maximizing impact, particularly in low-income and resource-constrained contexts where emissions reductions depend on coordinated demand- and supply-side interventions (Nilsson *et al.*, 2012).

Table 2. Assessment of coherence between forestry and clean cooking energy policies in Rwanda. (Source: Author’s original design)

Policy domain	Objective alignment	Operational integration	Synergy example	Key Conflict / Gap
Forestry Policy	High	Moderate	Forest restoration and afforestation contribute to national carbon sequestration targets	Demand-side fuelwood management weakly integrated into forestry planning
Clean Cooking Policy	High	Low	Improved cookstove adoption reduces household biomass consumption and emissions	Limited incorporation of sustainable biomass supply and forest conservation indicators
Overall Policy Coherence	Medium	Low–Moderate	Pilot projects linking clean cooking and forest conservation	Fragmented monitoring systems and absence of shared mitigation metrics

Source: Author’s original compilation from Primary and Secondary Data

5.5. Pathways toward Integrated Socio-Environmental Climate Mitigation planning

This study identifies several complementary pathways through which Rwanda could strengthen policy coherence and advance integrated socio-environmental climate mitigation planning. First, *regular and coordinated policy updates* that explicitly link forestry sustainability and clean cooking objectives would help synchronize sectoral priorities and reduce fragmentation across governance frameworks. Embedding cross-sectoral targets within national strategies would further support alignment between energy transitions and forest conservation outcomes.

Second, the development of *shared planning, monitoring, and evaluation frameworks* [supported by harmonized baseline data on biomass use, forest condition, and clean cooking adoption] would enhance evidence-based decision-making and accountability across sectors. Such frameworks could facilitate consistent tracking of mitigation outcomes while enabling learning across policy domains and implementation levels.

Importantly, moving beyond *project-based coordination toward institutionalized integration* would allow forestry and clean cooking policies to function as mutually reinforcing components of climate mitigation planning rather than as parallel interventions. This would require formalized coordination mechanisms, clearer mandates across institutions, and *strengthened vertical linkages* between national policy formulation and decentralized implementation.

Altogether, these proposed pathways align with Rwanda’s broader development and climate ambitions and highlight the potential for integrated planning to address persistent forestry–energy trade-offs. As illustrated in Figure 3, operationalizing integrated forestry and clean cooking

strategies could offer a scalable model for other countries confronting similar socio-environmental mitigation challenges.

Figure 3. Proposed pathways for strengthening policy coherence and achieving integrated socio-environmental climate mitigation in Rwanda.

Source: Author's original design

6. Conclusion

This study examined the coherence between Rwanda's forestry and clean cooking energy policies, exploring their interactions, synergies, conflicts, and implications for integrated socio-environmental climate mitigation. By combining document analysis, key informant interviews,

and secondary data, the study provided a comprehensive understanding of both policy intentions and practical implementation challenges.

Summary of results

Taken together, the findings demonstrate that Rwanda's forestry and clean cooking energy policies are strategically aligned but operationally fragmented. Document analysis revealed shared objectives across sectors but limited mechanisms for integration, while interviews highlighted practical coordination challenges and localized synergies. Secondary data contextualized the progress achieved and the gaps that remain, establishing a robust empirical foundation for assessing how stronger policy coherence could enhance integrated socio-environmental climate mitigation planning.

The research objectives were successfully achieved. The study mapped the linkages between forestry and clean cooking energy, examined institutional coordination dynamics, and evaluated the implications for climate mitigation. The research questions concerning policy alignment, operational conflicts, and potential integration pathways were addressed through triangulated insights from documents, expert interviews, and secondary data trends. Findings confirm that improved coherence could substantially strengthen forest conservation, reduce biomass overexploitation, and accelerate the adoption of cleaner cooking technologies, advancing Rwanda's climate mitigation goals.

Contribution to theory and practice

Empirically, this study demonstrates how policy coherence operates within a real-world socio-environmental system. The findings extend policy integration theory by showing that strategic alignment can coexist with operational fragmentation and that institutional constraints significantly shape climate mitigation outcomes. Practically, the study highlights actionable entry points for strengthening forestry–energy integration within Rwanda's climate and development planning processes.

Recommendations

- Update forestry and clean cooking energy policies periodically to reflect emerging socio-environmental trends and technological innovations.
- Establish formal coordination mechanisms between the Rwanda Forestry Authority, Rwanda Energy Group, local governments, and NGOs to strengthen cross-sectoral integration.
- Invest in baseline research and monitoring frameworks to generate robust data on forest use, biomass consumption, and clean cooking adoption rates.
- Promote community engagement programs that link clean cooking initiatives with sustainable forest management practices.
- Develop incentive schemes for households adopting cleaner energy solutions, reducing forest pressure while supporting socio-economic development.

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that achieving integrated socio-environmental climate mitigation in Rwanda requires both strategic alignment and operational coherence. By addressing identified institutional and policy gaps, Rwanda can harmonize forestry and clean cooking energy policies, ultimately advancing sustainable development and climate resilience objectives.

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